

FACTORS AFFECTING THE QUALITY OF AUDIT SERVICES

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Abstract. This article examines the issues about the level of quality of audit services provided, which have recently been increasingly discussed at various levels. Moreover, their results were not at all in favor of audit organizations. The same issue was raised at a seminar organized by the Audit Chamber of Uzbekistan at the end of June 2005.

Keywords: audit quality, audit risk, professional ethics, audit, accounting, auditor.

Introduction. Fair claims were made to the auditors about the quality of the services provided. It was noted at the seminar that the vast majority of audit organizations do not fully comply with the norms of national audit standards. Someone makes mistakes in planning, another in documenting the audit, etc.

During the discussion, some factors were formed, one way or another, individually or together affecting the quality of audit services of domestic auditors:

1. Insufficient qualification of auditors;
2. Misinterpretation of the provisions of the national audit standards;
3. The existing practice of potential clients ' work;
4. Dumping policy;
5. Lack of development of the branch network;
6. Centralization of services.

Let us consider in more detail the actions of these factors.

1. Insufficient qualification of auditors. It manifests itself in different qualities. Starting from the lack of a system of self-training of the auditor, to the lack of practical experience in some completely new field of economics for the

auditor. The lack of perfection of the quality control system of audit services in audit organizations only aggravates the situation.

2. Misinterpretation of the provisions of the national audit standards. A legislative framework has been formed in the republic that allows carrying out audit activities. National audit standards together constitute the legal framework through which auditors can plan and conduct audits. However, national standards consist of more general documents. Audit organizations should develop their internal documents based on them. Here the second factor begins to act. After all, the quality of the audit depends on how well these standards were understood and implemented.

At the seminar, it was noted that audit organizations do not comply with the requirements for documenting the audit, do not comply with the provisions of the national audit standard No. 5 "Quality control of the auditor's activities". This document indicates the need to develop internal documents reflecting the responsibility of the head for the organization of quality control of audit services, as well as for the creation and maintenance of a system of professional development of auditors.

3. The existing practice of working with potential clients. The quality of the audit is also influenced by the existing practice of some potential clients. As usual, they recall the need for a mandatory audit, at best, at the end of the year. Then the obstacle course begins. In a relatively short period of time, the auditors should study the activities of the customer and express their opinion on it. As usual, in such a hurry, something is necessarily forgotten or skipped. As a result, the quality of the audit suffers. Of course, the auditors have the right to refuse such an order. However, given the level of consumption of audit services, which is not in favor of our auditors, they agree. The family needs to be fed.

Another feature. Insufficient information about a potential client. Usually, the client, in the best intentions to show his desire for transparency, announces a tender for conducting an audit. At the same time, he does not provide the bidders with almost any information about himself. Interestingly, such cases are allowed

not only by our native domestic economic entity, but also by joint ventures and even international funds.

After all, in accordance with national and international auditing standards, an audit organization must conduct preliminary audit planning. In general, to study the scope and features of the company's activities, the level of accounting organization, etc., in order to determine the level of materiality and possible risks. Only after that, the auditors can name the cost of their services, or refuse to participate in the tender if the client is doubtful.

So it turns out that new audit organizations participate in such tenders in the dark, at random. All this affects the level of competition and the quality of the audit.

Some issues are likely to be resolved after the launch of the credit and information agency under the Association of Banks of Uzbekistan.

4. Dumping policy. In pursuit of a client, auditors sometimes compete with each other on the principle of who can offer the lowest price. Of course, this happens under the supervision of the audit client. And in the end, the same customer gets what his money was enough for. Not every auditor will thoroughly study the documentation of such a customer in order to give advice on optimizing his accounting and taxation.

5. The branch network is not developed. There are not so many audit organizations in the republic that have their branches in various regions of the country. As a result, when conducting an audit of the activities of an economic entity with branches in the regions, the audit organization usually attracts other auditors or audit organizations located in these regions on a subcontract basis.

Regardless, representatives of the audit organization itself will go to the regions to study the activities of the customer or entrust it to local auditors, but it will not always be possible to thoroughly document the audit or control the quality of the work of the involved auditors. In practice, there has never been a case when any audit organization held a competition among auditors for the right to work under a subcontract.

6. Centralization of services. This is a kind of the 5th factor. In some cases, in order to conduct an audit of an economic entity with republican subordination, an audit contract is concluded with a capital audit organization. A group of metropolitan auditors is arriving in the region. In a relatively short period of time, they should check and express their opinion about the activities of this subject. There are two opinions here: not all investors trust local auditors (a small city, everyone knows each other and does not want to offend) and visiting auditors cannot get acquainted with the client's activities in detail, collect the necessary information in a short time.

There is hardly an unambiguous solution to the above factors that negatively affect the quality of the audit. The complex of issues requires a comprehensive solution.

1. One of the possible ways to solve the issue is the consolidation of audit organizations, through the creation of alliances on a contractual basis or mutual mergers. A similar process occurs in foreign countries. And it manifests itself in some form in our country. This will lead to the emergence of large audit organizations (or groups of them), with an extensive branch network (or with a wide list of services, working practices in various sectors of the economy). As a result, a potential client will be offered a wide range of services and in such a large organization there is someone to control the quality level. Mutual support, mutual control and the opportunity to get advice directly from a colleague will undoubtedly play a positive role. It is necessary to stimulate this process at the state level.

2. It is necessary to organize and conduct explanatory work in the mass media to form the concept of the need for an audit in the economic life of the country. This function can be performed by professional public non-governmental associations of auditors. But they also need support. At least in the form of membership, with the payment of membership fees.

3. Organize thematic seminars on professional development of auditors in certain areas.

4. When insuring audit risks, the level of possible risk should be associated with the level of qualification of the auditors of the audit organization.

The Chamber of Auditors of Uzbekistan is carrying out certain work to improve the quality of audit services. Back in 2002, a draft Code of Professional Ethics of the auditor was developed. The manual "Audit techniques" was also developed, the book "Internal Audit in Commercial banks" was published. The adoption and implementation of the provisions of these documents contributes to improving the quality of audit services. The Chamber intends to translate the manual into Uzbek and republish it. The Chamber has put into practice the voluntary passing of tests after the completion of advanced training courses for auditors. Although this is not understood by all students of the courses, but the successful passing of the tests is evidence of the high level of knowledge of this auditor. The Chamber intends to further publish in the mass media a list of those auditors who voluntarily and successfully passed the tests after completing the courses. Thus, it is possible to provide them with indirect support, strengthen their image in society.

Currently, the Chamber is working on 3 projects that will somehow contribute to improving the quality of audit services.

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